

Self-protection against botnet attacks

Solutions by 5G PPP project SELFNET

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Cyber-attacks can affect both continuity and delivery of services. Such attacks threaten to directly affect subscribers of emerging 5G services. To protect them, 5G PPP project SELFNET has developed solutions particularly aimed at botnet attacks.

According to a statement from July 2014 by Joseph Demarest, Assistant Director in the Cyber Division at FBI, 18 computers per second are globally infected by a botnet. Botnets are one of the most powerful cyber threats subverting communication links. [1] That highlights the importance of detecting and dismantling botnets in any type of communications network. But in 5G, botnets pose an even greater security-related challenge due to the expected large number of connected devices with high mobility capabilities.

The detection and mitigation of botnets for improving security in 5G networks is the main goal defined in the self-protection use case of SELFNET (Framework for Self-Organized Network Management in Virtualized and Software Defined Networks) [2]. SELFNET is a Horizon 2020 project under the 5G PPP programme, which is devoted to designing and implementing an autonomic network management framework to achieve self-organizing capabilities in managing network infrastructures.

Enabling self-protection capabilities against botnets in SELFNET

The self-protection use case is designed to demonstrate the self-protection capability of the SELFNET solution in detecting and isolating compromised devices, also known as zombies, which constitute a botnet.

In a first step, the detection of a given botnet has been divided into two different detection phases, at two complementary levels of abstraction. In a first Self-Organizing Networks (SON) control loop, possible zombie devices are detected by identifying Command & Control (C&C) channels. These channels are discovered by analysing the network flows exchanged between the zombies and the C&C server, the botmaster in charge of controlling the zombies. As the type, size, and number of packages exchanged in a given period of time between the C&C server and different zombies is very similar, our solution is able to detect possible zombies. This SON control loop is due to the large number of connected devices expected in 5G networks, making it not possible to analyse all the traffic flooding the network.

Once a zombie is identified as a potential compromised device involved in a botnet, a second SON control loop of detection is carried out. In this case, fine-granular detection at low-level (Deep Packet Inspection, DPI) is required to ensure the existence of those C&C channels.

In SELFNET, this second phase is performed by a DPI tool like Snort, which is dynamically configured by SELFNET as a sensor. That dynamism is a must, because 5G subscribers, as entities with mobility capabilities, will be moving around the network, thus changing their network settings (mainly their IP address) constantly. Due

to that, the detection tools (Snort in this case) will be updated by SELFNET to continue performing their detection tasks on these mobile devices.

As a reaction to the previous detection, a virtualized and personalized honeynet is being configured as an actuator network function, in order to isolate potential cyber-attacks such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, which can be triggered by the botnet owner. Such a honeynet acts as a fake network: the detected zombies are logically placed as cloned zombies to emulate the behaviour patterns of each real zombie, by contacting the C&C Server, the main dashboard of the botnet owner, on behalf of the real, original zombie. From that moment on, the botnet owner will believe that the real zombie still exists, although it is not true. Subsequent cyber-attacks will not be carried out in reality.

Proof-of-concept prototype of the Self-Protection use case scenario

A proof-of-concept prototype demo of the primary self-protection use case scenario has been recently developed. This demo consisted of the following three steps:

Step 1. Traditional mode: SELFNET does not come into play.

A new zombie is recruited in a botnet, which is used to trigger an HTTP Flood attempt (DDoS at-

Figure 1: Proactive confirmation of a botnet through a DPI process

tack). This first step demonstrated, which problems a potential botnet could cause via a zombie launching a DDoS attack against a given victim.

Step 2. A suspected user end (UE) is detected as being part of a botnet (see Figure 1).

A DPI tool (Snort vIDS) is configured with a detection rule or signature to confirm that the suspected UE is an actual zombie. After that, a new flow rule is added into the virtual switch to enable the port mirroring feature, in order to send a copy of the raw network packets to Snort to be analysed.

As a result of this step, Snort will be able to generate alerts in IDMEF in case the UE is an actual zombie.

Step 3. A honeynet is configured to isolate the zombie communications to the botnet (see Figure 2).

This flow is diverted to the honeynet, named Traffic Diversion in Figure 2, in order to avoid the execution of a potential DDoS attack.

If the same HTTP flood attempt conducted in the first step is executed again, the victim will be not threatened by the attack. The victim is now protected by the SELFNET solution.

It is worthy to note that the demo showed the detection and mitigation of cyber-attacks conducted by a botnet in a proactive way, disabling the zombies' malicious behavior before they can be used as sources of a cyber-attack. The detection of 5G subscribers' devices as suspected zombies is defined in the Self-Protection use case of SELFNET, carried out through a first SON control loop, which was outside the scope of this first proof-of-concept prototype demo.

Conclusion

The solution proposed in the self-protection use case of the SELFNET project is able to detect and mitigate botnets in 5G networks. This proposal discovers C&C channels and therefore zombies using a detection process composed of two different phases. The first one is a low-granularity loop in charge of detecting possible zombies ana-

Figure 2: Isolation of compromised devices in a personalized and virtualised honeynet

lysing network flows. Once the possible zombies have been detected, the fine-granularity loop uses DPI tools to analyse the packages exchanged between the possible zombies and the C&C server. Finally, the reaction process consists of creating a virtualized honeynet where potential cyber-attacks such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) are isolated. In order to demonstrate the usefulness of our solution, we deployed a proof-of-concept prototype demo where the detection and reaction phases are shown.

As future work, and due to the high mobility of users in 5G networks, we plan to consider the users' location and their mobility in the detection and reaction processes. Specifically, when zombies and C&C servers move across different networks, it is required to identify and process locations in order to continue detecting and mitigating future attacks.

References

- [1] Joseph Demarest, "Taking down botnets: public and private efforts to disrupt and dismantle cybercriminal networks." Statement before the Subcommittee on Crime and Terrorism, United States Senate, July 2014. URL: http://www.judiciary.senate.gov/meetings/taking-down-botnets_public-and-private-efforts-to-disrupt-and-dismantle-cyber-criminal-networks
- [2] SELFNET – Framework for Self-Organized Network Management in Virtualized and Software Defined Networks, URL: <https://selfnet-5g.eu/>